

INFLUENCE OF NETT EDGES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF CARBON-FIBRE/EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon-fibre/epoxy panels with nett edges were produced from 8-harness fabric of 37% w/w resin content. Specimens with and without nett edges were tested for mechanical behaviour. The ultimate tensile strength, elongation to failure, tensile fatigue performance and impact strength were found to be very sensitive to the presence of resin-rich nett edges. Delamination was observed at the cut edges, whereas, specimens containing nett edges were prone to more insidious matrix cracking. Under compression, improvements were observed in the performance of the nett-edge containing specimens, although the influence of anti-buckling devices can be significant in these tests.

Keywords: Carbon fibre, epoxy, nett edges, resin richness, delamination, matrix cracking, mechanical behaviour,

1. INTRODUCTION

It is becoming increasingly important to understand edge effects in moulded composite products as the pressure increases to develop zero-waste manufacturing techniques that require no labour element for the finishing of the product. Therefore, the manufacture of nett-edge mouldings, eg. by resin injection into fibre preforms, as a possible replacement for the more "traditional" technique of moulding oversize and trimming to suit, becomes attractive. The nett-edge concept eliminates post-moulding trimming operations, hence, reduces fibre breakage, fibre/matrix disbonds, moisture absorption by capillary infiltration and scrap. These advantages, however, must be considered together with the resultant mechanical performance. The extent of susceptibility of the matrix to microcracking under tension can influence the failure mode of a continuous fibre reinforced polymer under fatigue (1, 2). A further complexity is the existence of high interlaminar stresses near the free edge of the laminate (3, 4, 5). Accordingly, the aim here is to compare the failure behaviour of carbon-fibre/epoxy test coupons which contain resin-rich nett edges with those of trimmed edges under static, dynamic and impact mechanical loading.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and Specimens

Carbon-fibre (CF)/epoxy panels were prepared from 8-harness-weave satin-fabric prepreg of 37% by weight resin content (Fiberite 934 resin and T300 3k fibre). A stack of eight prepreg plies of $(\pm 45^\circ)/(0^\circ, 90^\circ)/\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up configuration were laminated, after debulking and bagging, by autoclave curing at 180°C , 580 kPa for 2 hours. The flat cured panels of 3 mm x 193 mm x 940 mm had roughly 1.2 mm resin-rich nett edges. The panels were initially inspected by ultrasonic C-scanning and areas with greater than 0.5% void content were scrapped.

In order to obtain panels with straight nett edges, a picture frame type of tool was employed and sufficient clearance was left between the stack of prepregs and the tool bars to produce an arbitrary 1.2 mm wide resin-rich layer along the panel edges. The thickness of the periphery bars need to be carefully selected: significant variations from the expected cured thickness of the laminate can result in either a resin rich thicker edge or excessive resin flashing. Sealing tape was added to the outer edge of the periphery bars to act as a dam and reduce resin leakage.

Mechanical test pieces, with one trimmed edge and one nett-edge and also those with two trimmed-edges, were cut from the flat panels using a diamond tipped circular saw. Any sharp flash along the edges of the specimens were gently deburred by dry rubbing on 800 grit silicon carbide abrasive paper. Test pieces, Figure 1, for static and dynamic tensile and compression testing were 25.4 wide and 290 mm long and the ends to be gripped were clad with 1.2 mm x 25.4 mm x 80mm aluminium alloy tabs which were anodised with phosphoric acid and primed with an adhesive primer (Cyanamid BR 127) and then bonded to the abraded specimen ends using an autoclave curing epoxy adhesive (Cyanamid FM 73).

The specimens for microstructure examination were embedded in polyester resin and the surfaces to be examined were ground and then dry and wet polished in several stages of gradually increasing grinding media fineness.

2.2 Test Procedures

Tests were conducted at ambient temperature on specimens with both edges cut and specimens with one cut-edge and one nett-edge. The stress values for the nett-edge specimens were calculated in two different ways by (a) including, (b) excluding the resin-only edge layers in the width measurements. Static and dynamic tensile and compression tests, and impact tests were conducted using a Dartec servo-hydraulic universal tester, and an in-house built instrumented impact machine.

The results and observations recorded here are each based, at least, on two measurements for compression and tensile properties and six measurements for impact properties. Some of the specimens were partially loaded to various fractions of the fracture load in order to examine failure mechanism.

2.2.1 Static Testing

Strain gauges were bonded centrally to both faces of each tensile and compression specimens and aligned with the specimen centre-line. The specimens were tested at a stroke rate of 0.02 mm/sec, thus producing failure within 30-90 seconds. Some of the specimens were partially loaded to 30%, 60%

and 90% of the average ultimate-failure stress and examined, subsequently, under an optical microscope for incipient cracks or failure along the edges.

The compression specimens were supported with anti-buckling guides which had PTFE linings to reduce friction.

2.2.2 Dynamic Testing

Tension-tension and compression-compression fatigue tests in load control were conducted at 5 Hz sinusoidal loading. The lower stress level employed in each case was approximately 2.7 MPa whilst the upper stress levels ranged from 55% to 90% of the average ultimate static failure stress, thus producing a range of "cycles to failure" and hence allowing an S-N curve to be drawn. An anti-buckling device was employed for the compression tests.

Failure mechanism and damage progression was assessed by testing additional specimens at a load level known to produce an average fatigue life of 10^5 cycles. The specimens were temporarily removed from the test machine at time intervals of 10^3 , 10^4 and 5×10^4 cycles for ultrasonic C-scanning and X-radiography.

The surface temperature of the fatigue specimens were monitored by using a temperature probe, and at the test frequency of 5 Hz an insignificant temperature rise (4%) was recorded.

2.2.3 Instrumental Impact Testing

Test pieces (3 mm x 12 mm x 60 mm) were edge-on impact tested in 3-point bending, on a support span of 40 mm, at 1 m/s using an instrumented falling weight machine fitted with a 45° chisel-shaped striker of 3 mm tip radius. Specimens were placed such that either a nett edge or a cut edge received the direct impact hit. Incident impact energy was varied, by changing the mass of the projectile, to effect either complete fracture or damage of different magnitudes with complete load-deflection traces of the events.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 and Figure 2 show that the static and dynamic tensile properties of the nett-edge containing specimens, irrespective of the manner of the width measurements, are inferior compared with the both-edges-trimmed specimens. The reason is the premature failure of the test coupons due to weakness of the resin-rich nett-edge region under tensile loading. The matrix employed here is brittle, with a failure strain of 0.7% compared to a value of 1.5% for the fibre, and therefore, cracks are generated along the nett edges as soon as the test strains reach the value of the resin failure strain, well before the potential strains expected from the composite are reached. These transverse matrix cracks cause sufficient localised damage and stress concentration in the composite such that crack propagation across the test coupon occurs readily. The resin-rich edge forms a skin (or a mantle) around the outer $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, see Figure 3, and consequently these plies suffer localised damage upon the failure of the nett edge, exposing the longitudinal fibres to greater stresses. In fact, the 0° fibre tows may already incur a localised structural weakness by partial migration into the resin rich region as can be seen in Figure 3. A further source of weakness at the nett edge, which may contribute to the ease of propagation of a crack across the specimen, is the uneven distribution of the fibres through the laminate thickness at the interface with the resin-rich layer (cf. Figures 3 and 4). The manual method of production makes it very difficult to avoid the formation of this rugged fibre

distribution at the nett edge: the placement of the first prepreg ply of each panel at a desired distance from the periphery bars was achievable, however, accurate placement of the subsequent plies was more difficult as the resin-tack prevented easy ply positioning. This was exacerbated when laying the $+45^\circ$ plies as they could only withstand a limited degree of manipulation before the fibres in the weave become increasingly separated.

The lower ultimate tensile strength (UTS) values indicated by the nett-edge containing specimens is not a consequence of the reduction in the overall fibre content. Table 1 shows that UTS values computed based on width measurements excluding the width of the resin-rich edge layer produced only a small improvement, approximately 7%, compared to a 30% improvement observed in both-edges trimmed specimens. Similarly, the improvements indicated in the tensile fatigue performance of cut-edge specimens compared to nett-edge specimens as shown in Figure 2 are significantly beyond a magnitude attributable to fibre volume variations.

Table 1. Static fracture data under tension and compression

Specimen type	Tensile		Compressive	
	strength (MPa)	strain (%)	strength (MPa)	strain (%)
Cut-edge	402	0.88	458	0.80
Nett-edge ¹	308	0.77	462	0.88
Nett-edge ²	330	0.77	490	0.88

(1) including resin-rich edge in the specimen width measurement,

(2) excluding resin-rich edge in the specimen width measurement,

The sensitivity of the resin rich layer to the applied strain level is also evident under dynamic loading. The S-N curves for the specimens of both edge types show a convergence of the fatigue lifetimes at lower stresses. Obviously, the associated strains ($\approx 0.55\%$) are well within the failure strain of the matrix and thus do not readily produce the insidious transverse cracks in the resin.

The failure mode in the cut-edges was by delamination, between the (0° , 90°) and ($+45^\circ$) plies. These became visible at very high cycles and appeared to cause a progressive rather than sudden failure. For instance, delamination was detected by ultrasonic C-scanning, Figure 5, after 5×10^4 cycles and final fracture occurred at approximately 10^5 cycles. Delamination was not observed along the nett-edges since the onset of the laminated structure, in this case, is at least 1 mm in from the free edge, where the interlaminar shear stresses are much reduced. The free edge stress "boundary layer" is approximately equal to the laminate thickness, however, the shear stress decays exponentially within this region, reducing considerably even a small distance in from the edge (3).

Compressive static strength, Table 1, and fatigue performance, Figure 6, of the specimens containing nett edges indicated improvement when the stress calculations were based on the reduced cross-sectional area by excluding the resin-rich section. The reason for the improved performance is not obvious: the fibres receive additional support along the nett edge against any localised fibre buckling which is the usual cause of compressive failure,

however, no such support exists along the trimmed edge of the same test coupon. Furthermore, the $+45^\circ$ surface plies used here are not parallel to the applied load and hence less vulnerable to buckling (4). A plausible explanation of the variation observed between different specimen types under compression is also complicated by the need to employ anti-buckling guides. These rigs are known to affect the results by imposing various degrees of constraint on the specimen movement (6).

Impact load-deflection traces, Figure 7, show clear differences in the behaviour of the material depending on the type of specimen and also the type of edge struck: greater load values were registered for the crack initiation and propagation in specimens with both edges trimmed, but the nett-edge specimens required greater energy to failure initiation when the resin-rich edge received the blow, ie. undergoing compression. Whenever the resin-rich edge is subjected to tensile forces as shown in Figure 7-c, the specimen offers limited resistance prior to failure - particularly obvious is the lack of resistance to crack propagation.

Under 3-point edge-on impact loading, the test-pieces of the type of composites considered here initially suffer compressive failure until there is sufficient reduction in ligament area for the final failure to occur in tensile mode. However, the pattern of failure is reversed when the resin-rich edge is placed under tension: an initial sharp tensile crack forms across the resin-rich edge layer by either sufficient bending of the test-piece to reach the resin failure strain or due to impact shock waves. The failure of resin causes localised splitting/lifting of the $+45^\circ$ surface plies and the subsequent failure propagation becomes tensile dominated and moves from the lower edge upwards to the point of impact, producing a 'Δ' shaped pattern of failure as would be experienced in flexed-plate impact testing.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Differences between the behaviours of the test coupons containing resin-rich nett edges and those with only the cut edges are given below:
Specimens containing a resin-rich edge exhibited slight improvements under monotonic and dynamic compression, however, such magnitude of variations could easily be effected by the anti-buckling guides employed.

Nett-edge containing specimens exhibited inferior performance under edge-on drop weight impact. The extent of deterioration was found to be strongly dependent on whether a given edge was under compression (ie. the edge struck) or tension. The specimen offered almost no resistance to crack propagation when the nett edge was placed under tension and the manner of failure resembled that generated in a surface impacted composite panel.

An inferior tensile performance was indicated in the test coupons containing resin-rich nett edges, even when the results were normalised with respect to fibre content. A deterioration of 30% in the ultimate tensile strength and considerable reductions in fatigue life at a given stress were recorded, although a convergence in the fatigue lives of the different specimen types was indicated at lower levels of the applied stress/strain. Failure by delamination was clearly evident along the trimmed edges of the tensile fatigue test coupons but not along the nett edges. The mechanical weakness at the nett edges are related to the brittleness and, hence, ease of cracking of the resin, and also the fact that at the interface of the resin-rich layer the through-laminate-thickness fibre distribution is uneven, the $+45^\circ$ surface plies are vulnerable to localised damage and the 0° fibre tows to being dislodged.

The matrix in the prepreg system considered here has a strain to failure value which is significantly lower than that of the fibre, of course, there are alternative systems, from the same manufacturer and others, based on more ductile epoxy matrices and these are being evaluated in a similar programme of study.

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References

1. Curtis, P.T. and Moore, B.B., A comparison of the fatigue performance of woven and non-woven CFRP laminates in reversed axial loading, Int. J. Fatigue, Vol.9, No.2, pp. 67-78, 1992.
2. Wang, A.S.D., Strength, Failure and Fatigue Analysis of Laminates, in Engineered Materials Handbook, Composites, T.J. Reinhart, and C.A. Dostal, Ed. Vol.1, ASM International, Ohio 1988, pp. 236-251.
3. Pipes, R.B., 2nd Pagano, N.J., Interlaminar Stresses in Composite Laminates Under Uniform Axial Extension, J. Composite Materials, Vol.4, pp. 538-549, 1970.
4. Wang, A.S.D., Slomiana, M and Bucinell, R.B., Delamination Crack Growth in Composite Laminates, ASTM STP 876, W.S. Johnson, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1985, pp. 135-167.
5. Conti, P. and De Paulis, A., A Simple Model to Simulate the Interlaminar Stresses Generated Near the Free Edge of a Composite Laminate, ASTM STP 876, W.S. Johnson, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1985, pp. 35-54.
6. Matondang, T.H. and Schutz, D., The Influence of Anti-buckling Guides on the Compression-Fatigue Behaviour of Carbon Fibre-Reinforced Plastic Laminates, Composites, Vol.15, No.3, pp. 217-221, 1984.

Figure 1. A typical nett-edge specimen

Figure 2. Tension-tension S/N plots: (*) Cut-edge specimens, (●) nett-edge specimens including resin-rich edge, (○) nett-edge specimens excluding resin-rich edge in width measurements.

Figure 3. Micrograph showing a nett edge

Figure 4. Micrograph showing a cut edge

Figure 5. Ultrasonic C-scan of cut-edge specimen tested in tension-tension for; (a) 0, (b) 1000, (c) 10000 and (d) 50000 cycles.

Figure 6. Compression-compression S/N plots: (*) Cut-edge specimens, (●) nett-edge specimens including resin-rich edge, (○) nett-edge specimen excluding resin-rich edge in width measurements.

Figure 7. Impact traces for: (a) cut-edge specimen, (b) net-edge specimen with resin-rich edge struck, (c) net-edge specimen with trimmed edge struck